

**MARKET ANALYSIS TOOLS FOR SCALING SMALL BUSINESS
UNDER RESOURCE CONSTRAINTS: THE STRATEGIC APPROACH OF
AN INNOVATIVE ENTREPRENEUR**

Abstract. The article investigates the strategic use of market analytics tools for scaling small businesses under conditions of limited financial, human, and technological resources. It is substantiated that in the context of economic instability and increasing competition, the effective application of analytics enables businesses to adapt to external changes, supports informed managerial decision-making, and contributes to the optimization of operational activities without the need for proportional cost increases. The study outlines a typology of analytical approaches—descriptive, diagnostic, predictive, and prescriptive analytics—and analyzes their functional role in the strategic planning of a small enterprise. A range of free and freemium tools is considered, including Google Trends, Meta Business Suite, SimilarWeb, CRM systems, and BI platforms (such as Power BI and Tableau Public), which can be implemented even by enterprises with a low level of digital maturity.

Using the case of the women's clothing store UrbanLook in Uzhhorod, the study examines practical aspects of business scaling: assessing the attractiveness of locations for expansion, segmenting customers based on behavioral and demographic characteristics, optimizing procurement policies based on analytical data, and modeling energy consumption for opening a new point of sale. Special attention is given to the integration of digital tools for operational decision-making and demand forecasting, which enhances the efficiency of inventory and logistics management.

It is demonstrated that market analytics serves not only as a monitoring tool but also as a foundation for building a sustainable growth strategy for small businesses. The practical significance of the study lies in the development of differentiated recommendations for the implementation of analytical solutions according to the enterprise's stage of digital maturity, ensuring flexibility, competitiveness, and

sustainable development even under resource constraints. The scientific novelty consists in the substantiation of a strategic approach to utilizing accessible market analytics tools as a means of scaling small businesses under limited resources. For the first time, using a real case study, the integration of free digital solutions into the decision-making process based on multi-level analytics is demonstrated.

Keywords: small business, customer segmentation, CRM system, BI tools, analytics, demand, client.

Introduction (Relevance and Objectives). In the current context of economic instability, increasing competition, and resource scarcity, small enterprises face the urgent need to make strategic decisions based on accurate and reliable data. The survival and further scaling of a business largely depend on the entrepreneur's ability to adapt to a changing market environment, identify new growth opportunities, and effectively manage limited financial and organizational resources.

Within this framework, market analytics serve as a key instrument for supporting managerial decisions, enabling both retrospective and predictive analysis of consumer behavior, competitive dynamics, and internal business processes. An innovative approach to entrepreneurship implies the active integration of digital technologies, automated data collection systems, and business analytics, which opens new avenues for cost optimization, customer experience personalization, and overall operational efficiency enhancement—even under conditions of limited access to capital.

The aim of the study is to identify strategic approaches to the use of market analytics for scaling small businesses under resource constraints, using a practical case as an example.

Research objectives:

1. To analyze the types and functional capabilities of modern analytical tools suitable for small businesses.
2. To define the roles of descriptive, diagnostic, predictive, and prescriptive analytics in managerial decision-making.

3. To investigate the practical mechanisms of data-driven small business scaling (based on the case of the UrbanLook store in Uzhhorod).

4. To develop practical recommendations for implementing analytical approaches in enterprises with limited financial and human capacity.

Methodology:

– Systems analysis was applied to generalize theoretical approaches to market analytics and to structure them according to type and functionality.

– The comparative-analytical method was used to evaluate the effectiveness of various analytics tools (such as Google Trends, CRM systems, and BI platforms) within the context of small business operations.

– The case study method enabled an in-depth analysis of the scaling process of a clothing store in Uzhhorod, taking into account local factors and digital constraints.

– The data visualization method was employed to construct tables and figures that illustrate analytical processes and decisions in a business context.

– Empirical analysis was conducted to process actual data from CRM systems, online platforms, and consumer activity, which formed the basis for practical conclusions and recommendations.

Results. Market analytics is a systematic process of collecting, processing, and interpreting data about the external market environment, aimed at supporting strategic and tactical managerial decisions in business. It encompasses information on consumer behavior, demand dynamics, pricing strategies, competitor actions, and general market trends. The primary function of market analytics is to transform raw data into actionable insights that enable entrepreneurs to adapt to market shifts, identify risks, and discover growth opportunities (Lisnichuk & Yaroschuk, 2020, p. 113).

From a practical standpoint, contemporary market analytics is structured around four key approaches:

1. Descriptive analytics provides insights into past events, such as sales volumes, customer behavior, and seasonal fluctuations.
2. Diagnostic analytics identifies the causes behind observed trends—for example, why conversion rates dropped or why the return rate increased.
3. Predictive analytics models future scenarios based on available data, such as demand forecasts or customer loyalty estimations.
4. Prescriptive analytics generate optimal recommendations, including how to adjust pricing strategies, which promotion channels to use, or how to reallocate resources effectively.

The integration of these types of analytics into the management process of small businesses enhances the quality of decision-making, reduces uncertainty, and enables the formulation of evidence-based growth strategies, even under volatile market conditions (Cavallo, Cosenz, & Noto, 2023, p. 271).

Given the increasing complexity of market processes and the need for adaptive business models, market analytics no longer serves solely as a monitoring tool, but becomes a foundational element for the strategic scaling of entrepreneurial activity. It is through analytical data that businesses gain an understanding of potential growth areas, assess the efficiency of current operational processes, and design expansion scenarios without proportionally increasing expenditures (Richoux, 2023).

Scaling a small business in today's context is viewed as a process of structural and qualitative growth, involving enhanced operational efficiency, expanded market presence, and increased sales volumes, all while maintaining—or even optimizing—resource load. A key factor in this process is the capacity to implement technologies and analytical tools that allow for the automation of routine tasks, the identification of operational bottlenecks, and real-time decision-making.

Within this framework, the innovative entrepreneur emerges not only as the initiator of business activity, but also as a strategic integrator of digital solutions. Their managerial logic is grounded in the use of analytical tools, cloud services,

CRM systems, and data visualization platforms, which together ensure a high level of transparency, adaptability, and responsiveness in management. Such a proactive stance enables scaling not as an expansion of expenditures, but as intellectual growth through the optimization and technologization of business operations (Reshetnyak et al., 2024, p. 82).

In the context of strategic small business scaling, the selection of market analytics tools becomes particularly significant—tools that align both with the enterprise’s resource capacity and its level of digital maturity. Practice shows that even the effective use of basic tools enables small entrepreneurs to derive relevant insights into the market situation, consumer behavior, and competitor actions, thus forming a solid foundation for well-informed managerial decisions.

Analytical tools can be appropriately classified according to their functional categories and degree of accessibility:

1. Free general-purpose solutions such as *Google Trends* and *Meta Business Suite*.
2. Competitive analysis tools – including *SimilarWeb* and *SEMrush* (within the limits of free functionality).
3. Internal analytics tools – combining *Excel*, *Google Sheets*, and basic *CRM* systems.
4. Advanced BI tools – such as *Power BI* and *Tableau* (in free or trial versions).

At the early stages of business development, when access to in-depth internal analytics is limited, it is advisable to use universal platforms for real-time monitoring of the market and consumer behavior. These tools support rapid decision-making without requiring technical expertise (see Table 1).

Basic General-Purpose Analytical Tools for Small Business

Tool	Core Functions	Advantages	Limitations
Google Trends	Analysis of search query trends	Simplicity, rapid assessment of interest in topics/products	Does not provide detailed data on target audience behavior
Meta Business Suite	Social media audience statistics, demographic breakdown	Free of charge, integrated with Facebook and Instagram	Limited exclusively to Meta platforms

Source: Author's development

Google Trends and Meta Business Suite enable entrepreneurs to respond promptly to shifts in consumer interest and leverage these signals for initial product planning and launches.

Understanding market structure and competitor actions is crucial for positioning one's own business. Tools in this category allow for the development of an external competitive strategy, even within the limits of free functionality (see Table 2).

Table 2

Competitive Analysis Tools

Tool	Core Functions	Advantages	Limitations
SimilarWeb (Free)	Website traffic data, visitor sources	Identifying market leaders, analyzing channels	Limited features in the free version
SEMrush (Free Tools)	Keywords, basic SEO analytics	Content selection, identification of competitive niches	Partial access to data

Source: Author's development

Even limited access to competitive analytics provides significant support in decision-making related to advertising, SEO, and pricing strategies for small businesses.

Internal analysis tools allow for the tracking of customer behavior and financial metrics (see Table 3). The combination of spreadsheets and basic CRM systems forms a starter kit for building a systematic approach to data management.

Table 3

Internal Analytics and KPI Monitoring

Tool Suite	Core Functions	Advantages	Limitations
Excel / Google Sheets + CRM	Tracking LTV, repeat purchases, average order value	Flexibility, customization, automated reports	Manual work, requires setup
CRM Systems (e.g., HubSpot Free)	Customer segmentation, activity log	Intuitive interface, communication history tracking	Functional limitations of the free versions

Source: Author's development

For entrepreneurs advancing to the scaling stage, it is essential to use tools for visualizing large data sets, automating reporting, and building forecasts. BI solutions provide a deep strategic level of analysis (see Table 4).

Table 4

Business Intelligence (BI) Tools

Tool	Core Functions	Advantages	Limitations
Power BI (Free)	Dashboard creation, forecasting, segmentation	Flexible visualizations, integration with Excel and CRM	Requires analytical skills
Tableau Public	Public data visualization, interactive charts	Professional-grade visualizations, supports various formats	Public data, limited confidentiality

Source: Author's development

The use of BI tools is advisable at the stage of forming a long-term strategy. They improve the accuracy of forecasts and allow for more effective resource allocation during scaling (Kgakatsi, et al., 2024, pp. 644–645).

It should be noted that the effectiveness of any analytical solution is determined not only by its functionality but primarily by its ability to integrate into the entrepreneur's strategic planning. One of the fundamental points of such integration is the market segmentation process, which directly influences the relevance of communications, product assortments, pricing policies, and the choice of distribution channels.

Analytics in the segmentation process allows for moving from an intuitive understanding of the customer to a well-grounded model of consumer behavior, based on geographical, demographic, and behavioral parameters. For instance,

combining data from *Google Trends* and *Meta Business Suite* enables an assessment of demand dynamics in a specific region, identification of peak activity times, dominant age groups, and interests inherent to the target audience.

In practical terms, this translates into the ability of small businesses to optimize the localization of marketing campaigns, adjust the geographical reach of services, personalize content, and adapt offers to market microsegments. The application of these approaches reduces marketing expenses by focusing on high-conversion niches, as well as increases the likelihood of a successful MVP launch or local pilot project.

Effective segmentation of the target audience using market analytics is a key stage in strategic planning for small businesses with limited resources (see Table 5).

Table 5

Consumer Analytical Segmentation in Small Business: Data Structure and Practical Application

Segmentation Parameter	Type of Analytics	Data Source	Example of Application	Strategic Effect
Geographic	Descriptive	Google Trends, Meta Insights	Identifying areas with the highest demand for automotive services	Optimizing location of sales points
Demographic	Descriptive	Meta Business Suite	Identifying the dominant age group for targeted advertising	Enhancing the effectiveness of advertising campaigns
Behavioral	Diagnostic / Predictive	CRM system, Google Analytics	Analyzing repeat purchases and interactions with content	Creating personalized offers
Psychographic	Prescriptive	Surveys, social media analysis	Identifying audience motivations and values	Developing emotionally relevant brand messaging
Temporal	Descriptive / Predictive	Google Trends	Analyzing seasonality of demand for children's services	Flexible management of promotions and work schedules

Source: Author's development

Analytical segmentation allows for micro-targeting the audience, which, in the context of limited resources, enables small businesses to avoid excessive budget

dispersion and focus efforts on the most promising consumers (Anilovska, Lebedinsky, 2024).

After establishing a well-grounded model of the target segment, the next logical stage in the strategic cycle of the innovative entrepreneur is the validation of market hypotheses, which determines the feasibility of further investments. In this context, market analytics transitions from a descriptive tool to a dynamic means of validating the business model through the Lean Startup approach.

The Lean Startup methodology involves creating an MVP (Minimum Viable Product)—a product with the minimum features necessary to gather feedback from early users with minimal resource expenditure. In this process, market analytics tools allow for the real-time tracking of behavioral metrics (conversion rate, interaction duration, abandonment rate), analyzing qualitative feedback, segmenting reactions by user types, and adapting product functionality based on identified patterns (Richoux, 2023). The capabilities of MVP are illustrated in Figure 1.

For better clarity, it is useful to refer to the practices of companies like Airbnb and Dropbox, which successfully applied the MVP concept in their strategy. Both Airbnb and Dropbox used MVPs to validate their hypotheses and gather user feedback at the early stages of product development.

In the case of Airbnb, the founders created a simple website to test user interest in the concept of home rentals. They confirmed that people were indeed interested in renting out their homes and finding accommodation through the platform. This allowed them to obtain valuable feedback and data that helped them adapt the product and further develop the business.

Picture 1: MVP Capabilities

Source: Author's development

Dropbox also used an MVP by releasing a prototype of its cloud storage service. They tested whether there was a demand for such a product and received positive feedback from users. This allowed them to continue developing and refining their cloud storage, transforming it into a successful product.

These examples demonstrate how the use of MVP helped Airbnb and Dropbox quickly validate their ideas and receive feedback from real users. This enabled them to focus on developing and improving key features that were in demand in the market. They were able to successfully transition from a simple MVP to the development of large, popular platforms (MVP in software development: reduced time and resources).

After forming the basic product and ensuring a minimally viable user experience, the next critical stage is the rationalization of internal business processes, particularly supply chain management. Effective demand forecasting based on user behavior data and MVP conversion allows businesses to avoid excessive storage costs, minimize dead stock in warehouses, and simultaneously

ensure continuous customer service. In this context, analytics transitions from hypotheses testing to providing systematic support for operational stability (Pshyk-Kovalska, Semenets, & Brutsiak, 2024).

In addition to operational demand forecasting and inventory control, optimizing the supply chain in the modern environment requires accounting for the risks of supply disruptions, fluctuations in raw material prices, and the inertia of production and distribution processes. Integrating BI tools with ERP systems creates the foundation for building an adaptive supply chain capable of reacting to changes in input parameters—from currency fluctuations to changes in consumer behavior in real time. Based on this, businesses can make proactive decisions regarding the reorientation of logistics routes, modification of order volumes, or even changes in product composition considering component availability.

The application of machine learning algorithms for demand forecasting allows identifying hidden consumption patterns that are unavailable through traditional evaluation methods. This not only helps reduce unsold stock but also enables the formation of flexible pricing strategies, which improve inventory turnover and operational profitability. In the end, an optimized supply chain becomes not only a logistical but also a strategic and competitive advantage, allowing a business to scale without losing operational efficiency (Rangareddygari, 2024, p. 2677).

In the context of modern challenges for small businesses, particularly the need for data-driven decision-making with limited resources, applied case studies demonstrating real mechanisms of scaling with the use of analytical tools are especially relevant.

We selected the case of scaling the women's clothing store "UrbanLook" in Uzhhorod—a small business that has successfully operated in the central part of the city for two years and is now considering opening a second retail location. With a limited budget, a shortage of qualified personnel, and the need for rapid market adaptation, the business uses applied analytical approaches and energy-efficient solutions, focusing on practical feasibility and strategic thriftiness.

To assess the feasibility of opening a new store location, "UrbanLook" used a combination of Meta Business Suite (audience geolocation analysis), Google Maps Insights, as well as free versions of SimilarWeb Local and Perekaz (tracking competitors' presence through key regional search queries). The collected data revealed high online activity by clients in the Petefi Square area, which has a high concentration of fashion retail and convenient transport accessibility. The presence of nearby schools, office centers, and cafes—sources of stable pedestrian traffic—was also considered (Table 6).

Table 6

Comparative Characteristics of Potential Locations for Scaling the "UrbanLook" Store in Uzhhorod

City Area	Online Activity of Potential Customers (queries/week)	Number of Fashion Stores within 500 m Radius	Presence of Offices/Schools/Cafes	Estimated Pedestrian Traffic (people/day)	Conclusion on Location Attractiveness
Petefi Square	720	6	Yes	3800	High – strategically favorable
Svobody Avenue	410	3	Partially	2200	Medium – requires additional research
Mynayska Street	290	2	No	1500	Low – small traffic and weak cluster
Haharyna Street	180	1	No	1200	Very low – not recommended

Source: Author's development

The analysis shows that Petefi Square is the most promising location for expanding the "UrbanLook" store, as it combines a high level of online audience interest with intense pedestrian traffic and a favorable commercial environment. This approach helps to reduce risks when scaling, focusing on objective data.

Thanks to the Zoho CRM system (basic free plan), the company segmented customers based on purchase frequency, average check, and product preferences. It

was found that capsule collections of basic clothing generate the highest conversion, while sales of accessories and dresses are seasonal. This allowed for adjustments in the purchasing policy: the focus shifted to limited batches of bestsellers with the possibility of quick replenishment (Table 7). For visualizing trends, Google Sheets + ChatGPT plugin were used – an inexpensive way to build graphs and dashboards.

Table 7

Customer Preferences Analytics and Sales Dynamics by Product Categories at "UrbanLook" Store (Zoho CRM Data)

Product Category	Share in Total Sales (%)	Demand Seasonality	Average Check (UAH)	Conversion Rate (%)	Purchasing Strategy Decision
Capsule Collections (Basic Clothing)	42%	Minimal (stable demand)	870	18%	Main focus, regular replenishment
Accessories	20%	High (Spring/Summer)	290	11%	Limited batches in season, minimal stock outside season
Dresses	25%	High (Graduations, Holidays)	1240	13%	Purchases based on demand, focus on pre-orders
Outerwear	10%	High (Fall/Winter)	2150	6%	Small batch purchases, focus on end-of-season sales
Sportswear	3%	Low	760	3%	Temporary removal from the assortment

Source: Author's development

CRM Analysis revealed the most profitable positions and allowed adjusting the purchasing policy to real demand. Focusing on capsule collections of basic clothing with high conversion rates and stable seasonality ensures turnover without overstocking, which is critical for small businesses with limited budgets.

Considering the rising energy costs, the energy consumption of lighting, heating, and air conditioning systems for the second location was modeled under three different retail space scenarios. The calculations were done using a free online HVAC Load Calculator. The choice was made in favor of a space with natural lighting and autonomous electric heating, which will reduce monthly expenses by

18-22%. Additionally, LED lighting and a work schedule with daytime breaks, which align with peak demand hours, are planned.

Given the results of the empirical analysis of the scaling case for "UrbanLook" in a small business environment with limited resources, as well as the evaluation of the effectiveness of tools used in localization, assortment management, and energy consumption, it is appropriate to formulate typical strategic recommendations for businesses at various stages of digital maturity. A differentiated approach ensures both a quick start for small market players and sustainable growth through the implementation of systematic business analytics in the long term.

Recommendations:

For Beginners:

- Launch basic analytical tools (Google Trends, Meta Business Suite) to quickly identify demand, behavioral patterns, and assess competitive traffic at the district level or at points of presence. This helps you make initial management decisions regarding niche selection or business localization.
- Integrate a free CRM system (e.g., Zoho CRM or HubSpot CRM) to build customer segments, identify priority product categories, and track cyclical demand fluctuations, aiding in the development of a grounded purchasing policy at early stages.

Long-Term Strategy:

- Implement BI tools (Power BI, Tableau Public, Google Data Studio) to build integrated data visualization systems, automate regular reporting, and model consumer behavior forecasts. This not only increases the accuracy of management decisions but also reduces dependence on reactive situational responses amid market turbulence.

Conclusion and Practical Significance. Thus, the strategic use of market analytics enables small businesses to effectively adapt to conditions of limited resources and high competition. The implementation of flexible approaches to data analysis, digital tools, and customer-oriented strategies opens up opportunities for business scaling even in times of uncertainty. The results of the study confirm that

innovative thinking, combined with analytics, fosters growth, reduces risks, and contributes to the long-term stability of small enterprises.

The practical significance of the study lies in the development of algorithms and recommendations for entrepreneurs on implementing accessible analytical tools in the daily operations of small businesses. As a result of the proposed approach, market opportunities can be assessed, consumer needs can be identified, costs can be optimized, and growth strategies can be developed. This is especially important in a limited budget context, where the effectiveness of decisions is crucial for the survival and development of a business.

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